

Toward Autonomous Qualification of Aerospace Composites: From AI-Driven Calibration to Digital Estimation of Allowables

Navid Zobeiry, PhD (navidz@uw.edu)

Associate Professor, Materials Science & Engineering Department

Adjunct Associate Professor, Aeronautics and Astronautics Department

University of Washington

<http://composites.uw.edu>

BE BOUNDLESS

Aerospace Certification Process: Analysis Supported by Testing

Material Variabilities and Processing Uncertainties

Current Industry Approach

- > Current approach, requires engineers to manually set-up problems in a preprocessor, submit the simulation, and analyze the results. They rely on experience and know-how and repeat this process, until the model is calibrated.

CFACS: an Autonomous Framework to Assist Certification

Automatic Pre- and Post-Processing, and FE submission

Automatic Calibration and Optimization

Automatic Test Outlier Detection

Sensitivity Analysis & Uncertainty Quantification

Statistical Analysis, Advanced Analytics & Machine Learning

TIEBREAK
Mixed mode delamination

Fiber aligned MAT 261

MAT 138 Cohesive

2023 NAFEM World Congress Award

Patent# US20230252206A1
Patent# US12189376B2

Outliers in Small Data

Load-displacement Outlier Types

Example:
Open Hole
Tension (OHT) Test

Type 1: premature failure

Type 2: stiffness mismatch

Type 3: stiffness variation

Type 4: mismatch in jumps

Type 5: noisy data

Type 6: premature jumps

Noise and Outlier Detection

Tests Data

Features

Outlier Detection Methods

Results

Identify Outlier Type and potential Cause

Matrix of results

	Test 1	...	Test n
Method 1	Outlier		
...			
Method m		Outlier	

- **Type-1:** Pre-mature failure
- **Type-2:** Distant stiffness variation
- **Type-3:** Stiffness error test fixture influence
- **Type-4:** Nonlinear variation due to MV
- **Type-5:** Sparse & Noisy data
- **Type-6:** Unexpected sharp load drop

Noise and Outlier Detection: RPCA

- > RPCA (Robust Principal Component Analysis) learns the underlying low rank data (L) and noise (S), from the observed data (Y), by solving an optimization problem:

$$\text{minimize}(\|L\|_* + \lambda\|S\|_1) \text{ subject to } Y = L + S$$

Background: Gaussian Process Regression (GPR)

- > Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) models the unknown function using two key assumptions:
 - At each input, the prediction is a Gaussian distribution (mean + uncertainty).
 - Nearby points are correlated using a kernel function (e.g., smoother if inputs are close).

Small experimental data

$$Y(X)|D_n$$

Unknown True response

$$Y(X)$$

Probabilistic Machine Learning

$$D_n \sim N(\mu(x), \sigma^2(x))$$

Zone of confidence interval

$$\mu(x) \pm Z \times \sigma$$

Potential
Maximum

Potential
Minimum

Background: Shape of COV matrix (Kernel)

Dot product

$$\Sigma = x \cdot x' + c$$

Polynomial

$$\Sigma = (x \cdot x' + c)^3$$

RBF
(Radial Basis Function)

$$\Sigma = e^{-\gamma \|x - x'\|^2}$$

Mix

$$\Sigma = (x \cdot x' + c)^3 + e^{-\gamma \|x - x'\|^2}$$

Initial GPR Training

- > The initial GPR kernel was trained using prior simulation results. For each new case, it is then fine-tuned using a limited amount of data from that problem.

Example: Compact Compression
(15000 simulations)

FE Inputs (material models)

FE Outputs

Automatic FE Calibration using Machine Learning

Case Study 1: In-plane Shear

- HEXCEL IM7/8552, Layup – $[\pm 45]_5$
- 0.02" element size, ~12,000 elements
- In-plane MAT261, In-plane cohesive MAT138, Interlayer TIEBREAK
- Calibrated parameters: 2 (MAT138, splitting)
- Calibrated with 10 simulations to <2% peak load error

CFACS Simulation DIC Test

Case Study 2: Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)

- HEXCEL IM7/8552, UD Layup
- In-plane MAT261, Interlayer TIEBREAK
- Calibrated to <2% peak load error
- Calibrated parameters: 2 (delamination)
TIEBREAK: mode I fracture toughness
TIEBREAK: strength

Case Study 3

- HEXCEL IM7/8552
- In-plane MAT261, Interlayer TIEBREAK
- Calibrated with 11 simulations to 1% error
- Calibrated parameters: 6

MAT261 : fiber fracture toughness in tension

MAT261 : matrix fracture toughness in tension

MAT261 : matrix fracture toughness in shear-T

MAT261 : matrix fracture toughness in shear-L

TIEBREAK : mode I fracture toughness

TIEBREAK : mode II fracture toughness

CT Scan

Simulation

Task	Layup	Peak Load Error
Calibration	Medium (25/50/25) Laminate [45/0/-45/90/45/0/-45/90] _s	<2%
Validation	Soft (10/80/10) Laminate [45/-45/0/45/-45/90/45/-45/45/-45] _s	-3.5%
Validation	Hard (50/40/10) Laminate [0/45/0/90/0/-45/0/45/0/-45] _s	4.1%

Digital Estimation of Allowables

- Random Generator
- Material Models
- FE Analysis
- Machine Learning Analysis
- Test Data

Calibration

Base Coupon Tests
0° lamina
90° lamina

Testbed

Validation

Test Data:
Other Lay-ups and Geometries

MAPLE/ML: MAterials PLayground for Engineers powered by ML

Stochastic Integrated Process and Failure Analysis

Distributions of Inputs

- Resin:
 - Initial Degree of Cure
 - Strength
 - Fracture Energy
- Fiber:
 - Diameter
 - Strength
 - Fracture Energy
- Prepreg:
 - Matrix Weight Fraction
 - Fiber Areal Weight
 - Lay-up
 - Ply thickness
- Autoclave:
 - Heat Transfer Coefficient
 - Tooling Material and thickness
 - Temperature Cycle
 - Pressure cycle
 - ...

Processing

Residual Stresses

Ply-level Failure

A Multi-Fidelity Approach

COMSOL & Python
Low-fidelity FE
1000 simulations (<2 days)

COMSOL & Python
High-fidelity FE
50 simulations (<1 week)

SOBOL Sensitivity Analysis: Transverse Tensile Strength

HEXCEL AS4/8552

Initial Training and Fine-tuning Surrogate ML models

1000 Low-Fidelity FE
Data

Neural Network

Initial
Training

Fine-
tuning

50 High-fidelity FE
Data

Fine Tuning with High-Fidelity Data

Fine-tuning with high-fidelity data

Input Features

Output Features

x_1
 x_2
 x_3
 x_4
 x_5
 x_6
...

y_1
 y_2

Initial training with low-fidelity data

10 hidden layers

Uncertainty Quantification with Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)

Test Data: Transverse Strength

HEXCEL AS4/8552 [90]₁₁

Environmental Conditions

Trained NN + MCMC

Quantify Uncertainties

Resin Strength (Pa)

Volume fraction

Clarkson, E. (2011). Hexcel 8552 AS4 unidirectional prepreg qualification statistical analysis report. FAA special project no SP4614WI-Q, Report No NCP-RP-2010-008 Rev D," Wichita State University, USA.

Eskandariyun, Amirali, et al. "A Novel Machine Learning Framework for Digital Estimation of Allowables in Aerospace Composites." ASME Aerospace Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference. Vol. 87745. American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2024.

Lamina Level: Digital Estimation of Allowables

- 50 simulations were conducted using the distributions of inputs from previous step.
- Cross-ply Failure Simulation (LS-DYNA, MAT261)

- Matrix weight fraction
(normal|0.37|0.003)
- Autoclave Heat Transfer Coefficients
(normal|70|10) W/m²K (bag side)
- Autoclave Heat Transfer Coefficient
(normal|35|10) W/m²K (tool side)
- Matrix strength
(normal|79.7E6|7.97E6) Pa
- Matrix fracture energy
(normal|2.485|0.24) J/m²
- Fiber strength
(normal|3.578E9|0.35E9) Pa
- Fiber modulus
(normal|227.6E+9|6.5E+9) Pa
- Lamina fracture energy (90)
(normal|3270|430) J/m²

Lamina Level: Digital Estimation of Allowables

	Estimated (50 Simulations)	Experimental (19 tests)
Mean	1004 (MPa)	1003 (MPa)
C.V.	6.07 %	7.64 %
B-Basis Allowable	878 (MPa) (-2.6%)	901 (MPa)
A-Basis Allowable	785 (MPa) (-5.7%)	833 (MPa)

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Conclusions

- > We introduced a framework that integrates fast testing, high-fidelity simulations, and machine learning to enable autonomous calibration and digital estimation of allowables.
- > Key potential benefits:
 - AI-assisted screening of materials and lay-ups
 - Uncertainty quantification and risk-aware certification
 - Reduced reliance on extensive physical testing
 - Automated, efficient process qualification

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